

The Effect of Education Level, Per capita Income and Consumption on Economic Growth in Indonesia

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Abstract

Effect of education level, per capita income and consumption on economic growth in Indonesia. This study discusses macroeconomic indicators that are often found as determinants of government policies in increasing economic growth. This study uses the regression method by analyzing data on the entire population from 2010 to 2019 which seeks to find the relationship between education and economic growth, per capita income on economic growth, and consumption on economic growth. The results of the study show that all variables have a positive and significant relationship, the largest positive relationship is consumption, while the smallest positive relationship is education.

Key Word: Education Level, Per capita Income, Consumption on Economic Growth

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's economic growth is important in improving the economic structure of its citizens, because the increase in economic growth can be seen from the contribution of the community in increasing Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Indonesia, which is a developing country, has an estimate of improving the quality of development in terms of the economy and the welfare of its people.

GDP measures the flow of income and expenditure in the economy over a given period. Economic growth is related to the process of increasing the production of goods and services in the community's economic activities. To measure economic growth, the value of GDP used is GDP based on constant prices (real GDP) so that the resulting growth rate is the real growth that occurs due to additional production (BPS, 2020). The existence of balance in an economy is one of the targets in the context of improving the economy of a country. Based on the following table describes the projected economic growth through the business sector.

Table 1. Economic Growth by Business Field in Indonesia
 Year 2010 - 2019

Economic Sector	Year (Persen)									
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
1. Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	0,51	0,55	0,63	0,57	0,56	0,49	0,44	0,50	0,49	0,46
2. Mining and Quarrying	0,44	0,45	0,31	0,25	0,04	-0,32	0,08	0,13	0,17	0,09

3.	Processing Industry	0,86	1,38	1,24	0,96	1,01	0,94	0,92	0,9 2	0,9 1	0,80
4.	Electricity and Gas Procurement	0,08	0,06	0,11	0,06	0,06	0,01	0,06	0,0 2	0,0 6	0,04
5.	Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	0,01					0,01				0,01
6.	Construction	0,62	0,82	0,61	0,58	0,66	0,61	0,51	0,6 7	0,6 1	0,58
7.	Motor Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair	1,19	1,30	0,75	0,66	0,71	0,35	0,54	0,5 9	0,6 6	0,61
8.	Transportation and Warehousing	0,25	0,30	0,26	0,26	0,27	0,26	0,29	0,3 4	0,2 9	0,27
9.	Provision of Accommodation and Food and Drink	0,18	0,20	0,19	0,20	0,17	0,13	0,15	0,1 6	0,1 7	0,18
10.	Information and Communication	0,51	0,37	0,47	0,43	0,43	0,44	0,42	0,4 7	0,3 6	0,49
11.	Financial Services and Insurance	0,20	0,24	0,34	0,32	0,18	0,32	0,35	0,2 2	0,1 7	0,26
12.	Real Estate	0,25	0,22	0,22	0,19	0,15	0,12	0,14	0,1 1	0,1 0	0,16
13.	Company Services	0,12	0,13	0,11	0,12	0,15	0,12	0,12	0,1 4	0,1 5	0,18
14.	Government Administration, Defense and Mandatory Social Security	0,29	0,24	0,08	0,09	0,08	0,16	0,14	0,0 7	0,2 3	0,16
15.	Education Services	0,33	0,20	0,24	0,22	0,17	0,23	0,12	0,1 2	0,1 6	0,19
16.	Sosial Health Services and Social Activities	0,06	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,06	0,0 7	0,0 8	0,10
17.	Other services	0,12	0,12	0,09	0,10	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,1 4	0,1 5	0,19
	Indonesian economic growth	6,38	6,17	6,03	5,56	5,01	4,88	5,06	5,0 7	5,1 7	5,02

Source: BPS Indonesia, 2021

The regional economic growth rate during 2010 to 2019 shows developments that tend to fluctuate. In 2010, out of 34 provinces in Indonesia, 14 provinces had an economic growth rate above the national growth rate of 6.38%. In 2019, the national economic growth rate decreased to 5.02% percent, and as many as 22 provinces had a higher economic growth rate than the national one, but the provinces were different from the conditions in 12 provinces whose figures were below the national economy. This means that there are provinces that are able to improve their economy, on the other hand there are also provinces that experience a decline in their economic growth. With high economic growth, the job opportunities created will also increase, because an increase in production requires additional inputs, including labor input. From the number of workers in Indonesia, which dominates more than the educational

background at the secondary level, the following is the data on the distribution of people who completed secondary education.

Table 2. Number of Senior High School Graduates and Equivalent Some Islands in Indonesia

Source: BPS Indonesia, 2021

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the number of high school graduates (SLTA) has not been spread evenly across several islands in Indonesia, the people who finished secondary level graduates are more spread out on the island of Java from 2010 to 2019, then followed by Sulawesi Island which was the highest after Java. However, the lowest number of people who complete secondary level are still in Maluku & Papua Island. From these data, it can be seen that the unequal distribution of education has also caused a slowdown in economic growth in the region.

As a solution to educational problems, it is necessary to increase skills in entrepreneurship, Hasan (2018) stated that education can foster a healthy and conducive business climate for economic growth because it is not only developing quality human resources, having knowledge and skills and running technology. Then education can actively participate in the development process so as to increase income and ultimately encourage increased economic growth.

Per capita income according to Sukirno (2021) is a benchmark used as a rough measure in determining the level of prosperity of the population through income, this income component is obtained from the acquisition of Gross National Product (GNP) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) divided by the total population . Income can be described through per capita income earned per one person in a certain period. The following is Indonesia's per capita income which is described by per capita GDP as follows.

Table 3. GDP Per capita of Indonesia

Year	GDP Per capita
2010	28.778
2011	30.112
2012	31.520

2013	32.875
2014	34.128
2015	35.162
2016	36.469
2017	37.851
2018	39.339
2019	40.496

Source: BPS Indonesia, 2021

From the data above, it can be seen that Indonesia's per capita income tends to increase significantly every year, but there are still gaps in terms of per capita income in several provinces in Indonesia, for example from 2010 there were still 25 provinces that had per capita income below the national level, then until 2019 it increased by 26 Provinces that have per capita income below the national level, this shows that there is still an uneven distribution of income in almost most provinces in Indonesia. When it is seen that low GDP in developing countries also causes a decrease in per capita income as expressed by Todaro (2012) says that people who live in developing countries tend to have low incomes, on average they have a real level of per capita income. low when compared to developed countries. To overcome this, the problem in developing countries according to Dutt (2011) is that policy objectives should focus more on the distribution of income, poverty, and unemployment, rather than controlling inflation. It can be seen that the distribution is positively related to long-term economic growth. It is hoped that the increase in income will have implications for increasing consumption in several regions in Indonesia.

Table 4. Monthly Per capita Consumption in Indonesia

Year	Consumption
2010	371.330
2011	593.664
2012	633.269
2013	703.561
2014	776.032
2015	868.823
2016	946.258
2017	1.036.497
2018	1.124.717
2019	1.165.241

Source: BPS Indonesia, 2021

From the data above, it shows that the increase in public consumption has increased significantly but still does not fully explain that consumption in several provinces has increased beyond national consumption, in 2010 there were 10 provinces whose consumption had not yet reached national consumption, and by 2019 20 provinces had not yet reached national consumption. national. Even though national consumption continues to rise, there are still some inequalities in terms of public consumption.

Consumption in macroeconomics is consumption on a national scale that is issued by connecting the rate of expenditure with national income, this calculation is referred to as the

expenditure approach which measures the final amount of goods at the end of a certain period (Case & Fair, 2009).

Consumption is the main thing that is very important as a determinant of macroeconomic policy both in the short and long term. There are several main reasons. First, consumption affects short-term monetary policy because it shapes the business cycle. Second, people's decisions to consume are determined by savings and capital stock, wages, interest rates and long-term welfare levels so that they become determinants of monetary and fiscal policy (Iyke & Ho, 2020).

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach with regression analysis aimed to analyze, predict and find the effect of education level, per capita income and consumption on economic growth in Indonesia. The data used is sourced from BPS Indonesia data which includes 34 cross section data which indicates the number of provinces in Indonesia as well as time series data in this study from 2010 - 2019 which examines overall data for 10 years so that the sample to be taken is 340 samples taken of the entire population by combining cross section and time series data, which is called balance panel data. The analysis in this study can be written in the equation, namely:

$$EGROWTH_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 EDUC_{it} + \beta_2 INC_{it} + \beta_3 CONS_{it} + e_{it}$$

Information:

EGROWTH = Economic Growth

EDUC = Education

INC = Perkapita Income percapita

CONS = Consumption

e = Error; i = data cross section; t = data time series

β_0 = Constan

β_i = coefisien regresi

RESEARCH RESULTS

Panel Data Regression Analysis

There are three models in panel data estimation in this study, namely: the common effects model (PLS model), the fixed effect model (FEM) and the random effect model (REM) which can be explained through the following estimation table.

Tabel 5. PLS Test Result

Variabel/item	coefisien	Signifikan	Information
Education	0.972625	0.000000	Significant positive
Income percapita	0.853402	0.000000	Significant positive
Consumption	-0.314677	0.000000	Significant negative
R ²	0.952108		
Significant	0.000000		Significant

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2021

Tabel 6. FEM Test Result

Variabel/item	Koefisien	Nilai Signifikan	Information
Education	0.085766	0.000090	Significant positive
Income	0.355480	0.000000	Significant positive
percapita			
Consumption	0.386132	0.000000	Significant positive
R ²	0.995499		
Significant	0.000000		Significant

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2021

When the two models have been known then there is a test to find out which of the two models between Pls effect model vs fixed effect model which is called the chow test. The chow test in the study can be known through the table below.

Tabel 7. Chow Test

Item	Signifikan	Information
Cross-section F	0.0000	Better FEM
Cross-section Chi-square	0.0000	Better FEM

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2021

Tabel 8. REM Test Result

Variabel/item	Koefisien	Nilai Signifikan	Information
Education	0.524063	0.000090	Significant positive
Income	0.479459	0.000000	Significant positive
percapita			
Consumption	0.149638	0.000000	Significant positive
R ²	0.707387		
Significant	0.000000		Significant

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2021

After the next model is the random effect model, then a test to test which of the two models is between the random effect model vs the fixed effect model is called the Hausman test. Hausman test in research can be seen through the table below.

Tabel 9. Hausman Test

Item	Significant Value	Information
Cross-section random	0.0000	Better FEM

Source: Processed by Researchers, 2021

The results between the two tests, namely, the Chow and Hausman tests, the suitable model used in this study is the fixed effect model with the model estimation as follows.

$$EGROWTH_{it} = 0.722840 + 0.085766EDU + 0.355480INC + 0.386132CONS$$

The results of the probability $F_{count} 0.000 < 0.05$ which means that the level of education, per capita income, and consumption have a simultaneous significant effect on economic growth in all provinces in Indonesia. While the R-square value has a value of 0.995499 which means that 99.5% percent of the variation in economic growth in Indonesia is influenced by variations in

education level, per capita income, and consumption. While the remaining 0.5 percent is influenced by other factors not included in the study.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing using the EViews 10 application described in table 2, it can be seen that the coefficient is 0.722840, it can be explained that the level of education, per capita income and consumption are considered constant, there will be an increase in Economic Growth of 0.722840.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the level of education has a probability value of 0.0001 which is smaller than the significance value of 0.05 which indicates that the level of education has a significant influence on economic growth in Indonesia. The education level has a coefficient value of 0.085766 because the coefficient is positive which indicates a unidirectional relationship with economic growth which shows that if the education level increases by 1%, economic growth will increase by 8%.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Education Level on Economic Growth in Indonesia

Based on the results of hypothesis testing that the effect of per capita income partially has a probability value of 0.0001 which is smaller than a significance value of 0.05 which indicates that the level of education has a significant influence on economic growth in Indonesia

These results indicate a conformity with the previous researcher, namely Pegkas (2020) with his findings that there is a positive and significant relationship with education as human capital which is considered a channel in increasing economic growth. However, apart from that, its contribution to economic growth is less than other variables.

Mercan (2014) explains that education has a positive and significant relationship to economic growth, increasing education levels has a positive impact on economic growth by increasing labor productivity and knowledge production capacity. Therefore, the government must prioritize the mission of training quality workers. and productive with a system that makes it easy for the community to access education. Research Lin et al. (2021), Adejumo et al. (2021), Pushina et al. (2021), Su et al. (2021), Maneejuk and Yamaka (2021), Monterubbianesi et al. (2021), found that education investment can increase economic growth. Meanwhile, according to Le et al. (2021), Qi et al. (2021) investment in education can reduce income inequality. Research in Poland states that education spending policies can increase economic growth (Konopczyński, 2021). Montalbo (2021) found that the effect of education can increase economic growth. In contrast to the research of Doğanalp et al. (2021) stated that there was no effect of education on economic growth.

Then, according to Sharma (2018) In developing countries, international trade plays a key role in economic growth. and can certainly facilitate an environment led through trade assistance, the government is able to mobilize idle resources which ultimately towards the long-term economy. With this, the government needs to improve the education system that provides professional course education educational institutions

Hanushek (2020) educational mechanisms can affect economic growth. First, education can increase the human capital inherent in the labor force, which increases labor productivity and thus transitions growth towards higher equilibrium levels of output. Second, education can

increase the innovative capacity of the economy, and the development of new technologies, products and processes promotes growth. Third, education can facilitate the dissemination and transmission of knowledge needed to understand and process new information and to successfully implement new technologies designed by others, which can ultimately promote economic growth.

Based on the theory and findings from researchers, it can be concluded that education has a positive and significant influence on economic growth because education is a tool to increase one's input which is ultimately used as skills and productivity in designing results in the form of new technologies and outputs that contribute to economic growth. Thus, in testing the hypothesis that education has a positive and significant effect on economic growth, the truth can be tested.

The Effect of Per capita Income on Economic Growth in Indonesia

Based on the results of hypothesis testing that the effect of per capita income partially has a probability value of 0.0000 which is smaller than a significance value of 0.05 which indicates that per capita income has a significant influence on economic growth in Indonesia.

These results indicate a concordance with previous researchers, namely Ciurea (2010) who explained that the most affluent areas showed higher growth rates than elsewhere. This development must be accompanied by a reduction in the gap between regions in terms of economic potential so as to reduce regional inequality in terms of income.

According to Chaudhuri in Nissan (2008) defines economic growth as an increase in the output of goods and services, total or per capita, which is measured in value added continuously. The increase in total output is called "extensive", while the increase per capita is "intensive", where the focus of attention is the standard of living or welfare of the population. Thus, it can be concluded that per capita income explains the welfare and prosperity of the community in terms of income. Carrera et al. (2021) stated that per capita income reduces social inequality. While research López (2021), Khan et al. (2021), Murshed (2021) find that per capita income can sustain economic growth.

Some of the potential that have great opportunities and benefits in the future it is evident that the impact of education is able to expand the analysis of income and wages and the proportion of workers who work for a salary or wages which seems useful to explore measures that reflect the chances of most highly educated individuals being absorbed in the labor market which ultimately generates income for the individual and is ultimately used for his consumption purposes. Looking at the large contribution of per capita income to economic growth in Indonesia, it shows a very close relationship because economic growth is an increase in terms of income throughout the economic structure, while per capita income is the result of the division of output by the total population of the region (Kinh and Westbrook, 2012) . Based on the results of research and findings from experts, it can be concluded that the hypothesis that per capita income affects economic growth in Indonesia can be tested for truth.

The Effect of Consumption on Economic Growth in Indonesia

Based on the results of hypothesis testing that the effect of consumption partially has a probability value of 0.0000 which is smaller than the significance value of 0.05 which indicates that consumption has a significant effect on economic growth in Indonesia.

These results show a conformity with previous researchers Siman (2020) in his findings that income has a positive and significant impact on household consumption expenditures and vice versa because in fact the increase in public consumption or spending on goods produced from several business sectors contributes income which is then used for additional purposes. the production of output of an item that takes working hours than usual so that it will certainly increase economic growth in terms of consumption. When Indonesia's economic growth fluctuates due to disturbances and obstacles in several economic sectors due to lack of public spending, another finding says the ratio of consumption expenditures needs to be seen in terms of the income it receives, therefore, when an economic shock occurs, households have the capacity to protect its consumption of food, non-food and services when it declines along with per capita income (Kotelnikova & Radaev, 2017).

According to Magazzino et al. (2021), Villanthenkodath et al. (2021), Wang et al. (2021), Merlin et al. (2021), Liu et al. (2021) and Rahman, (2021) found that there is an effect of consumption expenditure on economic growth. Meanwhile, according to Witt (2021), Le and Park (2021) stated that an increase in welfare can increase consumption. While consumption increases economic growth (Tasmeea et al., 2021; Namahoro et al., 2021)

In other findings, it is argued that households must be productive in terms of increasing their income which ultimately also increases consumption. This is closely related to people who are careful in utilizing the money market through investment activities such as insurance, mutual funds, deposits, stocks, and other forms. Therefore, their consumption behavior is significantly influenced by the financial wealth created by the financial market so that later this in turn will result in an increase in the wealth of generational financial assets and consequently increase household consumption to encourage economic growth (Swamy, 2020).

Based on the results and findings of previous researchers that consumption has a positive and significant effect on economic growth, the truth can be tested because it can be seen in the research results that its contribution to economic growth is greater than other variables.

CONCLUSION

The variable level of education has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Indonesia. These results are in accordance with the theory developed which says that the higher the education, the economic growth will also increase, with more people who complete education at the secondary level believed to be able to increase their productivity, but judging from the results the coefficient is quite small that education at the secondary level is still small. its contribution to economic growth, therefore the Indonesian government must provide more improvements to educational and learning facilities that focus more on increasing their productivity so that the results can later be implemented in the world of work. Per capita income has a positive and significant influence on economic growth, this result implies that the relationship between these variables is quite close in increasing economic growth, when people already have qualified jobs with high incomes, which are expected to contribute greatly to economic growth. Consumption has a positive and significant influence on economic growth, from the results of the study it can be seen that the contribution of consumption is the largest among other variables because economic growth increases because people spend more of their income, both food and non-food for their consumption purposes, thus stimulating economic sectors which will encourage economic growth.

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